

Maxillary Sinus Augmentation in Implant Dentistry : A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract

Maxillary sinus augmentation is a cornerstone procedure in implant dentistry, especially for managing the atrophic posterior maxilla. This review explores the evolution of sinus lift techniques, anatomical and surgical considerations, graft materials, and post-operative management. Advancements such as piezoelectric surgery, antral-balloon-assisted elevation, and minimally invasive approaches have significantly improved outcomes. The article underscores the importance of individualized treatment planning and evidence-based approaches in ensuring long-term implant success.

Keywords : Direct sinus lift, maxillary atrophy, osseointegration, dental implants, congenital defects, surgical techniques, bone grafting.

Introduction

Over the last three decades, implant-directed maxillary reconstruction has increasingly relied on sinus augmentation grafting to overcome the anatomical limitations of the posterior maxilla. The region's challenges—low bone density, sinus pneumatization, and post-extraction alveolar bone loss—result in limited bone volume for implant placement^{1,2}. The spongy nature of maxillary bone makes it one of the least dense bones in the oral cavity. Following tooth loss—particularly due to periodontal disease—alveolar ridge resorption accelerates in the absence of functional stimulation. This may lead to a bone reduction of 40–60% within three years³, significantly impacting prosthetic rehabilitation. The maxillary sinus, with an average volume of 12.5 mL, lies bordered by the orbital floor superiorly and the posterior maxillary alveolus inferiorly. The Schneiderian membrane—a bilaminar mucoperiosteal layer—is vital during sinus lift procedures¹. The main goal of sinus augmentation is to increase vertical bone height for predictable implant osseointegration³. While the lateral window technique remains the gold standard, innovations like the transcresal approach, balloon-assisted elevation, and piezoelectric instrumentation offer minimally invasive alternatives with improved safety and recovery⁴. Understanding maxillary sinus anatomy, including the location of septa and neurovascular bundles, is essential for successful outcomes^{1, 5}. Despite significant advances, ongoing research

is required to improve graft materials, minimize surgical trauma, and enhance predictability. The integration of minimally invasive protocols and personalized planning is key to the success of implants in the atrophic posterior maxilla.

Historical Background

Sinus lift surgery dates back to the 1970s when Dr. Hilt Tatum⁶ introduced augmentation techniques using autogenous rib grafts. Later, he modified the Caldwell-Luc procedure by creating a lateral window, allowing Schneiderian membrane elevation and grafting. In 1994, Dr. Summer⁷ proposed the internal (crestal) approach using osteotomes. By 1996, Dr. Junji Chen introduced the hydraulic sinus condensing method, employing hydraulic pressure to lift the sinus floor⁸. These innovations significantly reduced morbidity and expanded the treatment scope for patients with posterior maxillary atrophy, setting the foundation for today's advanced sinus augmentation protocols.

Methods

A comprehensive electronic search was conducted using the PubMed database to identify relevant studies published up to the year 2019. The search utilized the keywords: Maxillary sinus, direct sinus lift, bone graft-

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ing, complications related to direct sinus lift. The aim was to include both prospective and retrospective follow-up studies on the placement of direct sinus lift. Studies with a follow-up period of less than Six months and case reports lacking adequate follow-up were excluded. The selected articles were then organized in chronological order to facilitate a clearer understanding of the progression and evolution of Direct sinus lift techniques.

Anatomical and Surgical Considerations

The adult maxillary sinus is a pyramidal, air-filled cavity measuring up to 45 mm in height and 15 cm³ in volume. Its floor lies approximately 1 cm below the nasal cavity and is closely related to the roots of maxillary premolars and molars. Internally, it is lined with pseudostratified ciliated columnar epithelium, which plays a key role in mucociliary clearance.⁹ Drainage occurs through the osteomeatal unit (OMU), and disruption due to anatomical variants like septa or accessory ostia may predispose to sinusitis. The sinus has six walls, each with vital anatomical landmarks such as the infraorbital canal (superior wall), the pterygopalatine fossa (posterior), and the maxillary alveolus (inferior).¹⁰ Accessory ostia (in 40% of individuals) and Underwood septa (in 58%) can complicate sinus surgeries. Understanding these structures is essential for accurate surgical planning.¹⁰

Blood Supply and Innervation

The sinus receives blood primarily from the posterior superior alveolar artery (PSAA) and infraorbital artery, forming an anastomotic network within the lateral wall. Injury to these vessels during surgery can cause hemorrhage or graft failure.¹¹ Venous drainage is via the facial vein and pterygoid venous plexus (fig.1).

Fig.1- Vascular system that innervates the maxillary sinus vestibular wall. The infraorbital artery and the posterior superior alveolar artery form an intraosseous anastomosis (dotted line). (IA: Intraosseous anastomosis, EA: Extraosseous anastomosis, IAR: Infraorbital artery, MA: Maxillary artery, PSAA: posterior superior alveolar artery).

Innervation is from the maxillary division (V2) of the trigeminal nerve, with contributions from the superior alveolar nerves and pterygopalatine ganglion. Lymphatic drainage is directed to the submandibular, retropharyngeal, and deep cervical nodes.¹⁰

Preoperative Evaluation

A comprehensive preoperative evaluation is essential before initiating surgical intervention. This should begin with a detailed medical history and physical examination, focusing on factors that may influence surgical outcomes. Important considerations include recent upper respiratory infections, chronic sinus conditions, sinus or facial pain, otitis media, previous nasal or sinus surgeries, and any prior attempts at maxillary reconstruction. Additionally, documenting the patient's smoking history is essential, as it may affect healing and graft success. A preoperative computed

tomography (CT) scan is highly recommended to assess available bone volume, detect any existing sinus pathology, and identify anatomical variations such as bony septae that may impact the surgical approach.

Surgical Technique: Lateral Window Approach

The lateral window approach, first described by Dr. Hilt Tatum,⁶ remains the gold standard for maxillary sinus augmentation. It allows extensive vertical bone augmentation - up to 12 mm - through a direct view of the Schneiderian membrane.

Anesthesia and Flap Design

Local anesthesia is typically administered using 2% lignocaine with 1:200,000 epinephrine or 4% articaine. Incisions may be midcrestal or palatal, depending on keratinized tissue and bone availability. A vertical releasing incision is added to enable full flap reflection. Sulcular or submarginal incisions may also be utilized when harvesting bone from the tuberosity region.¹⁰

Antrostomy Creation

The antrostomy is an oval or rectangular bony window (fig.2) created using rotary instruments or piezoelectric tips. The inferior horizontal cut is positioned 2–3 mm above the sinus floor. Variations include:

Fig.2. Antrostomy carried out using rotary instruments.

- Top-Hinge Trapdoor Technique :** In this technique, a rectangular osteotomy is created in the lateral sinus wall using round burs or piezoelectric tips, forming a U-shaped trapdoor. The inferior cut is made 2–3 mm above the sinus floor, while the superior cut is partially drilled to preserve bone thickness. The bony plate is then carefully fractured inward and repositioned medially, remaining attached to the Schneiderian membrane. This repositioned cortical plate serves as the superior border of the new sinus compartment, ensuring stability without exceeding the sinus width (fig.3).

Fig.3. Top-hinge trapdoor SFE.

- **Repositioned Bony Window:** This technique is typically used for thick lateral sinus walls and aims to preserve the buccal plate. A rectangular osteotomy is made using mechanical or piezoelectric tools, and the lateral window is carefully removed with a periosteal elevator. The bony window is separated from the sinus membrane, stored in saline, and later repositioned over the graft material without rigid fixation after membrane elevation.
- **Complete Osteotomy :** In this technique, the buccal bone plate is completely removed to create an access window. If the bone is thick, it is thinned using a round bur, piezo tip, or bone scraper until the bluish hue of the sinus membrane is visible. To minimize the risk of membrane perforation, the window is then refined using a diamond-coated bur or a smoothing piezoelectric tip.¹¹

Membrane Elevation

Using blunt elevators or piezoelectric inserts, the Schneiderian membrane is carefully dissected and elevated. Perforation risk is minimized by starting at the sinus floor and moving anteriorly and medially. In cases of thin membranes, a collagen membrane may be used for reinforcement.¹⁰

According to volumetric studies, around 5.46 cm³ of graft material is needed for 15 mm augmentation, and 3.5 cm³ suffices for three implants of 13 mm length.¹¹

Implant Site Preparation

Ideally, a minimum of 3–4 mm of residual crestal bone is needed for primary stability. Implants can be placed simultaneously if sufficient bone is present; otherwise, a staged approach is recommended.

Graft Placement and Closure

Autografts or substitute materials are packed along the sinus walls to encourage revascularization. Overfilling is avoided to reduce complications. The flap is repositioned and sutured to ensure tension-free closure.¹²

Balloon-Assisted Sinus Elevation (BASE)

A minimally invasive alternative, balloon-assisted sinus elevation (BASE) uses hydraulic pressure to lift the membrane. After crestal incision and buccal window formation, a balloon catheter is inserted and inflated with saline, gently elevating the membrane. This reduces trauma and allows simultaneous graft and implant placement.¹³

Piezoelectric Surgery in Sinus Augmentation

Piezoelectric instruments use ultrasonic vibrations to cut bone while sparing soft tissues. Introduced by Horton et al., this technique minimizes the risk of Schneiderian membrane perforation and preserves vascular structures.

Vercellotti et al. observed a 5% perforation rate with piezosurgery. Diamond-coated and ball-tip inserts are particularly useful for membrane detachment. Though technically demanding, this approach enhances safety and predictability.¹⁴

Graft Materials

Bone grafts are commonly utilized to stimulate bone regeneration, and maxillary sinus augmentation can be achieved using various materials, including autografts, allografts, xenografts, alloplastic substitutes, and growth factors. Autogenous bone graft considered the gold standard due to osteogenic, osteoinductive, and osteoconductive properties. Common donor sites include the iliac crest and intraoral regions. Autogenous chips promote neovascularization within a week due to bone morphogenic proteins (BMPs)¹³.

Allografts sourced from a donor of the same species, possess osteoconductive and osteoinductive properties but lack osteogenic potential. Demineralized Freeze-Dried Bone Allografts (DFDBA) contain BMPs, promote bone formation, and are gradually resorbed.¹⁰ Xenografts derived from bovine sources and used for their osteoconductive properties, though resorption may be slow. Synthetic substitutes materials like tricalcium phosphate and hydroxyapatite are used for volume maintenance and structural support. The success of grafting is influenced by porosity, biocompatibility, and surface chemistry.

Postoperative Care

Proper post-op care is crucial for healing and graft success:

- Avoid nose blowing, using straws, or applying pressure to the sinus.
- Apply cold compresses for the first 24 hours.
- Maintain a soft diet; removable prostheses should not contact the surgical site.
- Use chlorhexidine or saline rinses after 24 hours.
- Sneeze with an open mouth and avoid bending over.
- Analgesics and antibiotics are prescribed as necessary.¹⁰

Complications and Management of Sinus Lift Surgery

Sinus lift procedures may present with intraoperative, early postoperative, and delayed complications. Membrane perforation is the most common intraoperative issue, manageable with collagen membranes. Graft material loss may result from increased sinus pressure due to sneezing or inflammation. Bleeding from the lateral wall vessels can be controlled using bone wax or electrocautery. Postoperative complications include wound dehiscence, oral fistula formation, acute graft infections (5% incidence), and rare hematomas. Proper flap design, antibiotic use, and surgical technique reduce risks. Delayed complications like chronic sinusitis can occur from odontogenic infections, jeopardizing implant success if left untreated.¹⁵

Discussion

Implant placement in the posterior maxilla is often complicated by limited vertical bone height due to alveolar resorption and sinus pneumatization². Maxillary sinus augmentation, particularly through the lateral window approach, has become the standard of care for creating adequate bone volume to support osseointegrated implants.¹⁵ The lateral window technique allows for substantial bone height gain (up to 12 mm) and direct visualization of the Schneiderian membrane. Despite its advantages, this method is invasive and carries risks like membrane perforation and sinusitis.⁴ To minimize these complications, less invasive options such as the transcrestal (osteotome) technique have been introduced. While these offer reduced morbidity, their use is limited to patients with a minimum residual bone height of 6–7 mm.¹⁵ Antral balloon-assisted sinus elevation (AMBE) has shown promising results, enabling controlled membrane elevation with reduced risk of perforation. Soltan and Smiler (2005) emphasized its value in narrow ridges, making it a suitable choice for simultaneous implant placement.¹³ Piezoelectric surgery has transformed the way sinus lifts are performed. Vercellotti et al. (2001) reported a reduced membrane perforation rate (5%) using piezoelectric devices.¹⁴ These instruments selectively cut mineralized bone while preserving soft tissue integrity, enhancing surgical safety. Torrella et al. (1998)

also highlighted the precision and reduced complication rate with ultrasonic devices, although they require longer operating times and technical expertise.¹⁶ These benefits make piezoelectric surgery particularly valuable in anatomically challenging cases. Preserving the Schneiderian membrane is a critical determinant of sinus lift success. Perforations increase the risk of postoperative infections and implant failure.⁴ Preoperative cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) scans are invaluable for identifying sinus septa (seen in up to 37% of patients) and the proximity of the infraorbital nerve.¹⁷ In some cases, sinus elevation can be avoided altogether. Tilted implants, as described by Aparicio et al. (2001), achieved a 95.2% implant survival rate and a 100% prosthetic survival rate over five years.¹⁸ Zygomatic implants also offer a reliable solution for severely atrophic maxillae, with success rates as high as 97% (Candel-Martí et al., 2012)¹⁹. The choice of graft material profoundly impacts healing and implant success. Autogenous grafts remain the gold standard due to their osteogenic capacity, but their use is limited by donor site morbidity.²⁰ The Safescraper is one intraoral tool that facilitates safe autograft harvesting. Allografts and xenografts serve as viable alternatives with varying degrees of osteoconductive and osteoinductive potential. DFDBA, enriched with BMPs, supports bone regeneration, especially when used in well-vascularized environments (Goldberg & Stevenson, 1987)²¹. Aro et al. (1981)²² compared ultrasonic and oscillating instruments, noting that while early bone healing was slower with piezoelectric tools, long-term histological results were comparable. These findings justify the use of ultrasonic techniques for their tissue-sparing benefits. Residual bone height is a key predictor of implant success. Al-Dajani (2014) found that implants placed in bone with less than 5 mm height showed lower survival rates. This underscores the necessity of thorough radiographic and clinical planning. Brignardello-Petersen et al. (2014) promoted evidence-based dentistry (EBD), advocating for treatment planning based on high-quality research and individualized patient care.²³ In a retrospective study, Balaji (2013) demonstrated that the direct sinus augmentation technique resulted in a mean bone height gain of 6.19 mm, supporting its use in severely atrophic ridges.² The study also emphasized the importance of alveolar width in choosing implant diameter.

Conclusion

Maxillary sinus augmentation is a vital surgical technique that has evolved significantly over the years. From its origins in the 1970s to today's minimally invasive and technology-assisted procedures, the sinus lift has enabled the reliable placement of implants in the challenging posterior maxilla. The lateral window technique, though invasive, remains the most versatile and widely used method for substantial bone gain. Alternatives like the transcrestal and balloon-assisted approaches cater to patients with moderate residual bone, offering reduced morbidity. Technological innovations such as piezoelectric surgery and improved biomaterials have enhanced safety, reduced complications, and improved long-term outcomes. The selection of graft material, patient-specific anatomy, and adherence to postoperative care protocols are all crucial for success. As maxillofacial surgeons, it is our responsibility to stay abreast of these advancements and apply them with precision and personalized planning. With the aid of CBCT imaging, careful anatomical evaluation, and evidence-based decision-making, we can ensure optimal functional

and esthetic outcomes for our patients.

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